

ISSUES OF FORMATION OF YOUTH PREPARATION FOR FAMILY LIFE

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Abstract: This article deals with the training of learners for family life, psychological, ethnic features of the problem, skills of family relationship and about in the formation of family life in adolescents, taking into account our nationality, national and family values

Keywords: Family, youth, ethnic characteristics, psychology, social, national, parent, preparation for family life, upbringing.

1. INTRODUCTION.

The modern family and its problems serve as the object of study of a number of disciplines - psychology, pedagogy, sociology, demography, economics. Experts are studying the dynamics of emotional relationships in marriage, the causes of loneliness in the family and its breakdown, the peculiarities of family upbringing. In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PF-5325 dated February 2, 2018 "On measures to radically improve the activities in the field of support of women and strengthening the family" developed proposals for preparing young people for family life on the basis of rich cultural heritage and traditional family values output and implementation are among the main tasks. The decree emphasizes the need to carry out targeted work to prepare young people for family life, to form a modern exemplary family, to strengthen its spiritual and moral foundations and traditional family values. The tasks of the state in this area are to strengthen the family, to build family relations on the basis of mutual love, trust and respect, solidarity, mutual assistance and a sense of responsibility of all its members, to ensure the unimpeded exercise and protection of their rights. The need for knowledge, experience, advice, recommendations to perfect these tasks, of course. The concept of "family" has its own inner meaning for everyone. For a child, it is the mother, father, brothers, sisters, grandparents, uncles and aunts involved in his upbringing

2. THE MAIN PART.

For a young man after marriage, the family is first him and his young wife, then the children. At present, family reunification has not become a necessary factor for spiritual and physical survival. The person has gained relative independence from the family, the nature of perception of family relationships has changed. In the early stages

of family life, a wave of new emotions softens the problems and contradictions that arise in marriage. During this period, the unfavorable situation in the family, internal conflict between husband and wife is almost not reflected in external relations. Failure to prevent the accumulating tension will result in a change in mutual understanding, trust, and anchor points between the two couples, and over time this will lead to a sharp conflict. As Virginia Satir points out, starting a family is the hardest job in the world, so preparing for family life is very important, even at the state level. The stability of family relationships largely depends on the readiness of young people for family life, where readiness for marriage is understood as a system of socio-psychological relations of the individual, which determines the emotionally positive attitude to family life. The reason for the low level of preparation of children and adolescents for family life is that, in recent years, E.G. According to Silyaeva, for many modern girls, motherhood is not accepted as a separate attribute of family and marriage. Z.G. According to Kostyashkina, "sex education is a separate part of moral education. Its distinctive theme is the complex and delicate skill of cultivating a relationship between a person of the same sex and another, and the ability to behave and control oneself in this regard." The introduction of weekly (1015 minutes) classes on family values for children over 4 years of age in preschool institutions in the country, the introduction of the subject "Fundamentals of Family" in grades 5-7 and "Family Ethics and Psychology" in grades 8-10. requires psychologists to pay attention to these issues. L.B. According to Schneider, the main difficulties in preparing the younger generation for family life are related to:

- problems with the development of criteria for preparation for family life;
- with difficulties in monitoring the results of training;

Consequently, preparation for family life is a complex socialization of young people in general

and solves the problem of parenting. The main problem in addressing this issue is that there are currently no

clear independent disciplines in secondary schools that perform this function.

The introduction of psychology and family psychology classes in schools can enable young men and women to find themselves in this world, to develop themselves and to know themselves, to help them overcome the difficulties and dangers of present and future life, and to take a conscious approach to their future. Helping a growing person is the main task and main meaning of a teacher and psychologist:

1. To form a general understanding among schoolchildren about what psychology and family psychology are and what it deals with;
2. To form an understanding of the importance of psychological knowledge in life and how they benefit people;
3. Self-awareness, understanding of human relationships;
4. Formation in adolescents of ideas about the family, its importance in human life;
5. Develop the following characteristics of adolescents: the ability to understand the other person's situation and problems, to be patient, to forgive people's shortcomings, the ability to establish friendly relations with loved ones, which should have a positive impact on their future family life;

The goal is achieved by solving psychological and pedagogical tasks that ensure the formation of the student's personality:

- formation in students of general ideas about psychology and family psychology as a science;
- help them to discover the inner world of a person, to arouse interest in other people and themselves;
- development of the intellectual sphere (general and special abilities, cognitive orientation, etc.);
- development of self-awareness (self-esteem, self-worth);
- development of self-awareness (self-esteem, self-worth);
- reveal the essence of personality orientation (needs, desires, goals, meanings, ideals, values);
- development of the emotional sphere (emotions, experiences, moods, etc.), understanding of other people's feelings and experiences;
- Identify and address negative attitudes in students' habits and behaviors.
- fostering in students an emotional and value attitude to man, activism, creativity, psychological culture, knowledge, aspiration to be healthy;
- Formation of ideas: about the moral foundations of the relationship between a boy and a girl, about partnership, about friendship and love, about the behavioral culture of lovers; about the different social roles of people in the family: the mother, wife, husband, etc., the responsibility of parents for the life and health of the child, the responsibility for the upbringing of children; about the features of children's development and the main problems of child rearing; about the economy and family

life, about the basic income and expenses of the family; on the basics of family law; on the ethical rules of human behavior in cases of conflict or family breakdown.

According to Yu.B. Shapiro, one of the problems that complicates the quality preparation of adolescents and young people for family life is the lack of human resources due to the lack of targeted training in higher education.

Nevertheless, in the United States, this problem has a national status and is successfully addressed through the training of specialists in the relevant field.

In this case, we need to give the following recommendations to parents and pedagogical psychologists:

- increases the positive coverage of family life in the media;
- High competence of psychologists conducting consulting work;
- separate explanatory work for boys and girls in preparation for family life is carried out by male and female psychologists;
- It would be expedient to organize a seminar with parents of adolescents by school practicing psychologists on preparation for family life

3.CONCLUSION.

A teenager brought up in such a psychological environment can feel free to be a pillar in acquiring the necessary knowledge in family life. At the same time, if such training is carried out on the basis of comprehensive cooperation with parents, relatives, teachers, peers and others, adolescents will gain knowledge about marriage and family relationships and will form an idea about life

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